

SEARCH FOR NEW LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART V

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Several basic amides and anilides have been synthesised and the local anaesthetic activity of some of them has been studied.

In continuation of our previous work (Gupta *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 655, 902; 1957, 34, 71, 528) compounds of the types (I) and (II) fulfilling the essential structural requirements of a local anaesthetic, namely a lipolytic end containing an aromatic structure, a hydrophilic end and an intermediate chain, have been synthesised.

In compounds of the above mentioned general types, the intermediate chain consists of a methylene-phenylene unit $-\text{CH}_2-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$; the replacement of the alkylene group by phenylene group may increase the lipolytic moiety. Basic esters have been reported (Fellows *et al.*, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1941, 73, 27; Fellows, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1943, 53, 7; *Chem. Abs.*, 1943, 37, 4472; Shriner *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 946), where α -methylene group of tertiary aminoethanol chain has been replaced by naphthalene or substituted benzene nuclei. These esters show varying degrees of anaesthesia, though some of these compounds are toxic and irritant in action. Fellows (*loc. cit.*) found 2-diethylaminomethyl-4:6-dimethylphenyl *p*-amino-benzoate to possess good local anaesthetic activity in 0.5 to 1% solution. The introduction of $-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}<$ unit in aromatic nucleus may potentiate the activity.

Braun (*Arch. Klin. Chir.*, 1903, 69, 541) showed that the addition of epinephrine or its analogues potentiated the action of local anaesthetics. An attempt has therefore been made in the synthesis of compounds of the general type (III).

For the synthesis of compounds of type (I), 3-(*N*-piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxyaniline and its analogues, prepared according to the method of Burckhalter *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1363), were treated with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride. The products were then reduced and the bases converted into their hydrochlorides.

Compounds of the general type (II) were prepared by the action of an acid chloride (anisic, toluic, cinnamic) with 4-amino- α -*N*-piperidino-*o*-cresol and its analogues. The

latter were prepared according to Burckhalter (*loc. cit.*). The products were then converted into their hydrochlorides.

Compounds of the type (III) were synthesised by treating 3-(N-piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxyaniline with chloroacetyl chloride. The chloroacetylated product was condensed with a secondary amine. The bases are sticky substances and have been characterised by converting them into their solid derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *3-(N-Piperidinomethyl)-4-methoxynitrobenzene*.—A mixture of 2-methoxy-5-nitrobenzyl chloride (50.4 g), prepared according to Burckhalter (*loc. cit.*), piperidine (42.5 g.) and absolute ethyl alcohol (100 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 7 hours. Alcohol was then distilled off and the oily mass transferred into a beaker and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. It was then allowed to stand in an ice-bath for 2 hours, when it solidified to a yellowish mass. It was collected and crystallised from alcohol (90%) in yellow needles, m.p. 72-73°, yield 45 g. (Found: N, 10.9. $C_{13}H_{15}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11.2%).

2. *3-(N-Piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxynitrobenzene* was similarly prepared by refluxing a mixture of 2-ethoxy-5-nitrobenzyl chloride (53.8 g.), piperidine (42.5 g.) and absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) on a water-bath for 7 hours. The nitro compound was crystallised from ethanol (85%) in shining thick needles, m.p. 76°, yield 52 g.

3. *3-(N-Piperidinomethyl)-4-methoxyaniline*.—The compound No. 1 (37.5 g.) was reduced by a solution of stannous chloride (142.2 g. in 170 c.c. of conc. HCl). The flask was heated in a steam-bath for 5 hours with occasional shaking. It was then cooled in an ice-bath and the contents poured slowly into a beaker containing ice-cold solution of sodium hydroxide (210 g. in 420 c.c. of water). The temperature in the beaker was not allowed to go beyond 30°. The amine was extracted with ether and the extract dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. After removal of the ether, the residue was solidified in a freezing mixture. It was crystallised from pet. ether (60-80°) in brown needles, m.p. 61°, yield 23 g. (Found: N, 12.3. $C_{13}H_{20}ON_2$ requires N, 12.7%).

4. *3-(N-Piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxyaniline* was prepared in a similar manner as the methoxy analogue by reducing the compound No. 2 (39.6 g.). The amine was crystallised from dilute alcohol in light brown needles, m.p. 83°, yield 25 g. (Found: C, 71.5; H, 9.09. $C_{14}H_{22}ON_2$ requires C, 71.7; H, 9.4%).

5. *3-(N-Piperidinomethyl)-4-methoxy-N'-p-nitrobenzanilide* (I: X = NO₂; R = Me; B = piperidino) was prepared by adding slowly *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (4.3 g.) in dry benzene (10 c.c.) to compound No. 3 (4.4 g.) in dry benzene (15 c.c.). After refluxing for an hour benzene was distilled off and the residue treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The yellow powder was collected and washed thoroughly with water. It was crystallised from ethanol (85%) in shining needles, m.p. 162°, yield 5.0 g. (Found: N, 11.2. $C_{20}H_{25}O_4N_3$ requires N, 11.3%).

6. *3-(Diethylaminomethyl)-4-ethoxy-N'-p-nitrobenzanilide* (I: X = NO₂; R = Et; B = diethylamino) was prepared in the usual way, by condensing *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (4.3 g) with 3-(diethylaminomethyl)-4-ethoxyaniline (4.4 g.), prepared

according to Burckhalter (*loc. cit.*) in dry benzene. The nitro compound was collected and crystallised from ethanol (90%) in shining plates, m.p. 121°, yield 4.5 g. (Found: N, 10.95. $C_{20}H_{25}O_4N_3$ requires N, 11.32%).

7. 3-(*N*-Piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxy-*N'*-*p*-nitrobenzanilide (I: X=NO₂; R=Et; B=piperidino) was similarly prepared by condensing *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (4.3 g.) with compound No. 4 (4.7 g.) (Burckhalter, *loc. cit.*). The nitro compound, isolated as before, was crystallised from alcohol (80%) as a yellow powder, m.p. 91°, yield 5.5 g. (Found: N, 11.1. $C_{21}H_{25}O_4N_3$ requires N, 10.96%).

8. 3-(*N*-Piperidinomethyl)-4-methoxy-*N'*-*p*-aminobenzanilide Dihydrochloride (I: X=NH₂; R=Me; B=piperidino).—The compound No. 5 (4 g.) was reduced as before with SnCl₂ (14 g. dissolved in 17 c.c. of conc. HCl) and kept at 75-80° for 4 hours. The mixture after being cooled in an ice-bath was treated with NaOH solution (21 g. in 42 c.c. of water). The precipitated base was collected and washed with water and crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and petroleum ether (40-60°) in small needles, m.p. 174°, yield 2.2 g.

The hydrochloride of the base (2 g.) was prepared by dissolving it (2 g.) in absolute alcohol and saturating the solution with dry HCl gas. After removal of alcohol, the solid residue was collected and crystallised from absolute alcohol as a whitish powder, m.p. 239° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.95; Cl, 16.94. $C_{20}H_{25}O_2N_3 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 10.19; Cl, 17.2%).

9. 3-(Diethylaminomethyl)-4-ethoxy-*N'*-*p*-aminobenzanilide dihydrochloride (I: X=NH₂; R=Et; B=diethylamino) was similarly prepared by reducing compound No. 6 (4.0 g.) with stannous chloride solution (14 g. in 17 c.c. of conc. HCl). The base was crystallised from absolute alcohol and petroleum ether (40-60°) mixture, m.p. 226°, yield 2.1 g.

The hydrochloride of the base was prepared in ether solution of the base (2 g.) with hydrogen chloride. Ether was distilled off and the residue washed with ether. It was then crystallised from absolute alcohol and dry ether mixture as a whitish powder, m.p. 241° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.20. $C_{20}H_{27}O_2N_3 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 10.14%).

10. 3-(*N*-Piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxy-*N'*-*p*-aminobenzanilide dihydrochloride (I: X=NH₂; R=Et; B=piperidino) was also prepared in a similar way by reducing the corresponding nitro compound (4 g.) with stannous chloride and HCl. The base crystallised in plates from alcohol (80%), m.p. 167°.

The hydrochloride of the base, prepared in absolute alcohol in the usual way, was crystallised from absolute alcohol-ether mixture, m.p. 254°. (Found: N, 10.0. $C_{21}H_{27}O_2N_3 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 9.85%).

11. 4-(*p*-Toluamido)-2-(diethylaminomethyl)-phenyl *p*-Toluate (II: R=*p*-Tol; B=diethylamino).—4-Amino- α -diethylamino-*o*-cresol dihydrochloride was prepared according to Burckhalter (*loc. cit.*). The dihydrochloride (5.3 g.) was basified with sodium bicarbonate solution and thoroughly extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. The solution freed from ether gave an oily residue which was dissolved in dry benzene (20 c.c.) and was allowed to react with a solution of *p*-toluoyl chloride (6.2 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.). After refluxing

for 3 hours, the solvent was distilled off and the residue washed twice with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water. The product obtained was a pasty mass, which after crystallisation from dilute alcohol (charcoal) melted at 170°. Hydrochloride of the base crystallised from absolute alcohol-ether mixture, m.p. 271°. (Found: C, 75.3; H, 6.91; N, 6.5. $C_{27}H_{30}O_3N_2$ requires C, 75.34; H, 6.97; N, 6.51%).

12. 4-(Anisamido)-2-(diethylaminomethyl)-phenyl *p*-Anisate (II: R = $CH_3O.C_6H_4$; B = diethylamino).—The base obtained from 4-amino- α -diethylamino-*o*-cresol dihydrochloride (5.3 g.) afforded with anisoyl chloride (6.8 g.) a pasty mass which was, however, purified after several crystallisations from dilute ethyl alcohol (charcoal), m.p. 170°. (Found: N, 5.75. $C_{27}H_{30}O_3N_2$ requires N, 6.0%).

13. 4-(*p*-Toluamido)-2-(*N*-piperidinomethyl)-phenyl *p*-Toluate (II: R = *p*-Tol; B = piperidino).—The dihydrochloride (20 g.) of 4-amino- α -*N*-piperidino-*o*-cresol (Burckhalter, *loc. cit.*) was basified with sodium bicarbonate solution. The base was purified by crystallisation from petroleum ether (60–80°), m.p. 86°. The purified base (4.1 g.) in dry benzene (15 c.c.) was treated with *p*-toluoyl chloride (6.2 g.) in dry benzene (15 c.c.). The tolyl derivative was purified by repeated crystallisations from dilute alcohol, m.p. 148°. The hydrochloride ex absolute alcohol had m.p. 260° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.2. $C_{26}H_{30}O_3N_2$ requires N, 6.3%).

14. 4-(Cinnamido)-2-(*N*-piperidinomethyl)-phenyl *p*-cinnamate (II: R = $C_6H_5.CH=CH-$; B = piperidino) was prepared by treating 4-amino- α -*N*-piperidino-*o*-cresol (4.1 g.) with anisoyl chloride (6.8 g.). The product was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 220° (decomp.). The hydrochloride was crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. above 300°. (Found: N, 5.9. $C_{30}H_{31}O_3N_2$ requires N, 6.0%).

15. 4-(Anisamido)-2-(*N*-piperidinomethyl)-phenyl *p*-anisate (II: R = $CH_3O.C_6H_4$; B = piperidino) was prepared in a similar manner by treating 4-amino- α -*N*-piperidino-*o*-cresol (4.1 g.) with anisoyl chloride (6.8 g.). The product crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 152° and the hydrochloride from absolute alcohol-ether mixture, m.p. 267°. (Found: N, 5.76. $C_{28}H_{30}O_3N_2$ requires N, 5.90%).

16. 3-(*N*-Piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxychloroacetanilide (III: B = Cl).—A solution of chloroacetyl chloride (6.8 g.) in dry benzene (15 c.c.) was added slowly to 3-(*N*-piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxyaniline (14 g.) in dry benzene (25 c.c.). After refluxing in a steam-bath for one hour, benzene was removed. The residue after treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution was extracted with benzene. Benzene was nearly distilled off and petroleum ether (25 c.c.) was added when a solid mass separated. It was crystallised from benzene and petroleum ether (60–80°) mixture as a white powder, m.p. 121°, yield 10 g. (Found: N, 8.5. $C_{16}H_{23}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 9.0%).

17. 3-(*N*-Piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxy-*N'*-piperidinoacetanilide Dihydrochloride (III: B = piperidino).—A mixture of the chloro compound (3.1 g.) and piperidine (1.7 g.) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) was refluxed and the sticky base isolated in the usual way. It was converted into its hydrochloride, which was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol-ether, m.p. 139°. (Found: N, 10.08. $C_{21}H_{33}O_2N_3 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 9.72%).

18. 3-(*N*-Piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxydiethylaminoacetanilide monopicrate (III:B=diethylamino) was prepared in a similar way, as described above, by condensing the chloro compound (3.1 g.) with diethylamine (2.9 g.) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.). The base being a semi-solid mass and its hydrochloride being hygroscopic, the compound was characterised as a picrate. The picrate was crystallised from acetone and absolute alcohol mixture in yellow needles, m.p. 196°. (Found: N, 14.7. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_3 \cdot C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 14.5%).

19. 3-(*N*-Piperidinomethyl)-4-ethoxy-*N'*-morpholinoacetanilide picrate (III:B=morpholino) was also prepared in a similar manner by condensing the chloro compound (3.1 g.) with morpholine (1.7 g.) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.). The base and its hydrochloride were sticky masses which could not be crystallised. The picrate of the base was therefore crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 93°. (Found: N, 14.3. $C_{20}H_{21}O_3N_3 \cdot C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 14.23%).

Compounds No. 8, 9 and 10 have been tested at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, for local anaesthetic activity. None of the compounds showed any surface anaesthetic properties in 2% solution according to the method of Chance and Lobstein (*J. Pharmacol.*, 1944, 82, 203). When tested for intradermal anaesthesia according to the method of Bulbring and Wajda (*ibid.*, 1945, 85, 78) in 2% solution in normal saline, the action started after one minute and lasted for 90, 95 and 85 minutes respectively with inflammatory reaction. The compounds are being further studied for their pharmacological activity.

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